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Editorial

Nanomaterials as multifaceted structural and functional materials

Jominy Joseph¹, Robin Augustine^{2,3*}

Managing editor¹, Editor², AICM

³Biomedical Research Center (BRC) and College of Engineering, Qatar University, Doha, Qatar

*Corresponding author: Robin Augustine (robin@robinlab.in)

In the past decade, nanotechnology has presented huge growth in terms of multifaceted applications of nanomaterials in diverse fields such as energy, environment, aerospace, electronics and medicine (1). This issue of AICM covers the selected abstracts of papers presented at the International Online Conference on Nano Materials (ICN 2021) held during 9 – 11, April 2021 at Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala, India. Active participation of scientists, researchers, students, and leaders from various fields of nanoscience and nanotechnology including those who are exploring the possible application of nanostructured materials in materials science, chemistry, physics, biomedical engineering, polymer technology, electronics, automobile engineering, biotechnology, and other fields made this event a majestic success.

The conference was attended by hundreds of chemists, physicists, biologists, technologists, doctors, and engineers, making it indeed an interdisciplinary conference. Some of the selected abstracts of this issue cover a brief discussion on the synthesis, characterization, and physical properties of nanomaterials such as cobalt nanostructures. Some other experts reviewed the properties and recent advances in the application of nanostructured materials such as nickel and magnesium ferrite in the field of energy, environment, electronics, and biomedical applications. Singh and coworkers presented their important findings on the use of graphene-based materials in automotive engines for efficient heat transfer. Yadav and Alegeonkar showcased interesting research focused on the EMI shielding application of nanocomposites. Tomar and Jeevanandam discussed the development and application of magnetically separable adsorbents for the removal of toxic dyes. Prof. Dharuman from Alagappa University, India detailed the use of lipids along with graphene nanostructures for DNA sensing. Researchers like Maurya and coworkers discussed the role of nano fly ash hybridization on the thermomechanical properties of sisal fiber reinforced polypropylene nanocomposites. The industrial application of biodegradable nanofluids as lubricants in the machining industry was also discussed. A few researchers stressed the importance of adopting green synthesis approaches for generating metallic or metal oxide nanoparticles such as copper oxide nanoparticles. Yet, some others stressed the importance of formulating novel green polymer nanocomposites for a wide variety of applications. Several researchers discussed the application potential of nanomaterials such as hydroxyapatite as tissue engineering scaffolds.

Such discussions provided useful information regarding the importance of developing novel nanomaterials for diverse applications in industries. We hope that abstracts presented in this issue will help to foster the advancement of scientific research on these topics and result in meaningful conversations.

Keywords: *Nanotechnology, Nanomaterials, Nanomedicine, Composites, Biomaterials, Sensors*

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